

On the Effect of Visible Light Irradiation on Bilirubin and Bilirubin bound to Serum Albumins : An Insight into the Phototherapy of Neonatal Jaundice

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Free aqueous bilirubin is photodegraded very fast by visible light, even at the low intensity 0.06 W cm^{-2} . Both human and bovine serum albumins effectively protect this photodegradation of bilirubin; human serum albumin being marginally more efficient. Spectral analysis of the dialysate of albumin-bilirubin complex, exposed to visible light, indicates the presence of intact bilirubin along with the photodegraded products.

Next to the prophylactic use of vitamin K injection and silver nitrate or other eye drops, jaundice in newborn infants (neonatal jaundice) may be the most common reason for therapeutic intervention during this period of life. In fact, because we are so concerned about the potential toxic effects, particularly on the neonatal brain, everyday, physicians around the world subject thousands (perhaps millions) of infants to phototherapy, exchange transfusion, or other forms of therapy.

Bilirubin IX α (4Z, 15Z), the end-product of the normal breakdown of heme of hemoglobin in the red blood corpuscle (RBC), is the pigment of jaundice¹. Phototherapy has been in practice as a routine treatment of neonatal jaundice from time immemorial, of course, without understanding the mechanism thereof. Many researchers tried to elucidate the chemical structure of bilirubin and its photoproducts² as well as mechanism of phototherapy³⁻⁶. Initial belief, supported later by experimental evidences, that during phototherapy BR is photooxidized to smaller water-soluble fragments like methylvinylmaleimide, hematinic acid, dipyrroledialdehyde and propendyopents⁶, cannot explain the quantitative aspect. It has been established that only 10% of the total pigment is excreted as photodegraded products in urine and intact water-soluble bilirubin is also excreted during phototherapy^{7,8}. During phototherapy serum albumin-bound bilirubin undergoes conformational changes from the normal hydro-phobic intramolecularly hydrogen bonded (4Z, 15Z) form to the water-soluble (hydrophilic; principally : [4Z, 15E] and [4E, 15Z]) form and is easily excreted accounting only 15-20% of the total pigment⁸⁻¹².

We describe here a simple *in vitro* experiment to study the effect of visible light on free aqueous solution of bilirubin IX α (4Z, 15Z) as well as its complexes with human and bovine serum albumins (HSA and BSA).

Results and Discussion

Aliquots of the experimental solution were taken out at different intervals of time and the spectrum quickly read; the solution in the cuvette was poured back into the experimental bulk solution after recording the data. Fig. 1 shows the change in O.D. at the λ_{max} of HSA-BR, 460 nm,

Fig. 1. Absorbance decay versus time of exposure curves of $17.0 \mu\text{M}$ bilirubin bound to HSA (at specified BR/HSA) buffered at pH 7.6 (at 23°) exposed to a radiation density of 0.06 W cm^{-2} .

Fig. 2. Absorbance decay versus time of exposure curves of $18.2 \mu\text{M}$ BR bound to BSA (at specified BR/BSA) buffered at pH 7.6 (at 23°) exposed to a radiation density of 0.06 W cm^{-2} .

at different time intervals, due to photodegradation of BR bound to HSA; there were three sets of solutions at BR to HSA mole ratios of 0.25, 0.50 and 1.00 respectively. The result does not indicate a significant difference on the rate of photodegradation on BR/HSA ratio. Fig. 2 shows the similar set of results for BSA-BR complex; the changes of absorbance were recorded at 472 nm, the λ_{max} of BR bound to BSA. The percent degradation of free bilirubin (aqueous solution) as well as its complexes with BSA and HSA, at

1 : 1 mole ratios, at different exposures are summarized in Fig. 3. It is immediately obvious that unbound BR is degraded much faster than protein-bound BR, in support of the earlier reports⁵⁻¹⁰ and in contradiction to the view of Ostrow³ and, Ostrow and Branham⁴. Our result is also in parity with the observation that free BR fades faster than its protein complex even in the normal laboratory light, in fact the protein-BR complex did not fade at all even when exposed to laboratory light for as long as more than 8 h. A careful scrutiny of the results (Fig. 3) indicates that the

Fig. 3. Percent absorbance decay versus time curve of free BR and its albumin complexes; buffered at pH 7.6 (at 23°) exposed to a radiation density of 0.06 W cm⁻².

BSA-BR complex is relatively a bit more sensitive than HSA-BR. This observation is in parity with the result of Rubaltelli and Jori³, but our repeated observations show aqueous unbound BR to be more sensitive to photodegradation than that reported by these authors.

The spectra of the BSA-BR solution, exposed to visible light at an intensity of 0.06 W cm⁻², at different intervals of time are shown in Fig. 4; the spectrum (A) is at 0 min exposure followed by 220 min exposure finally upto (B). A solution of similar composition of BSA-BR (10.0 ml) in a dialyzing tube was placed in a bulk solution (15.0 ml) of BSA only of the same strength as in the dialyzing tube. The whole set was exposed to visible light of similar intensity and absorption spectra of the outer solution (dialyzate) read at different intervals of time, and are shown in the same figure. At zero minute exposure, the spectrum of the outer solution obviously merges with the base line, but with increase of exposure time the spectra start taking shapes eventually to D after 300 min of dialysis under exposure. It is interesting to note that the spectra at short exposure do not show any hint of a definite peak and look like the end-absorption of compounds having λ_{max} much below 370 nm. Probably they represent the photodegradation products of BR^{6,8,12}. Spectrum (D) shows a peak, though very broad

Fig. 4. Spectrum (A) is the absorption of BSA-BR (2 : 1); [BR] = 8.2 μM ; (B) is the spectrum (A) after 220 min, the solution was exposed to a radiation density of 0.06 W cm⁻²; (C) and (D) are the spectra of the outer solution of equilibrium dialysis experiment after 80 and 300 min respectively, which was also exposed to a radiation density of 0.06 W cm⁻² (at 23°).

around 465 nm, close to that of BSA-BR. This indicates that, on long exposure to visible light, bilirubin in BSA-BR probably photoisomerizes to a more hydrophilic isomer (like, [4Z, 15E] and [4E, 15Z])^{8,9} which eventually diffuses out from the dialyzing bag, and is subsequently complexed by BSA in the outer solution. The similar controlled dialysis experiment without exposing the contents of the dialyzing tube to intense visible light shows that the absorption spectra of the outer solution at different intervals of time (at least upto 6.0 h) does indicate the diffusion of bilirubin from the dialyzing solution—showing that our above speculation is not irrational.

Experimental

Bilirubin, bovine and human serum albumins (essentially fatty acid free, fraction V powder; Sigma) were used. Servapor dialysis tubing (29 mm) was obtained from SERVA, Germany. All other chemicals used were of A.R./G.R. grade.

Prior to each experiment, an aqueous alkaline solution of bilirubin was made by dissolving the pigment (3.0 mg) in 50.0 mM NaOH solution (2.5 ml) and the volume made up to 50 ml by glass-distilled water. Since the solution being highly sensitive to light, air and temperature, it was wrapped by aluminium foil and kept in cool dark place. Solutions of albumins were made in 10.0 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.6) as described earlier¹³. The strength of the solutions were calculated according to their molecular weights.

Dialysis : The dialysis sac (2–3 ft) was placed in a boiling water-bath (1.5 dm³) containing NaHCO₃ (5.0 g) and 2.0 mM EDTA disodium salt 1 h and stored in EDTA (10⁻⁴ M) solution, and washed in distilled water before use. Prior to each dialysis experiment, the tube was equilibrated against a solution of the same composition of the respective experimental solutions for 12 h to minimize the error in estimation due to adsorption of the components on fresh tube. A buffered solution of BSA-BR was dialyzed against a BSA solution. Here, we made the dialysis experiment in two sets : one set dialyzed in the dark and the other set dialyzed in irradiated condition as described earlier^{10,13}.

Irradiation of the solutions : Our experimental set-up was simple or rather crude. The experimental solution (20.0 ml) placed in an outer container (where water at 23° was circulated to nullify the heating effect of the radiation) was stirred by magnetic stirrer. A 200 W tungsten filament lamp (source of visible light) was placed above the experimental solution so that the distance between the center of the bulb and center of the experimental solution was 20 cm, a rough calculation gave a radiation density of 0.06 W cm⁻². All the experimental solutions were buffered at pH 7.6 by 10.0 mM phosphate buffer. The absorption spectra as well as absorption at specified wavelength(s) were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-160A spectrophotometer at 23°.

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